

DISTANCE LEARNING AS A FORM OF TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE.

Berdimurodova Oynakhol Bozor qizi¹

N.N.Panjieva²

Supervisor:,Phd

¹⁻²Master student of Pedagogical Institute
of Termez State University

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Annotation: This article is devoted to one of the forms of education, distance learning, which is relevant today. The article discusses the types of education, mainly distance learning, the benefits and motivational approaches for students.

Key words: distance learning, education, fully correspond, approach, skill, knowledge, abilities.

Today, speaking about the educational process, teachers consider various forms of education. The fact is that those training systems that were quite effective and productive in the past do not fully correspond to current realities. Modern human capabilities and the needs of society require completely new approaches and forms of education. School pedagogical councils and methodological associations of teachers are full of information about the use of new means of communication and new technologies in teaching, allowing students to develop all the necessary knowledge, skills and abilities individually. The teacher can transfer part of the material to self-study.

In modern education, the concept of "distance learning" has become increasingly used, and in pedagogical practice it is understood as one of the forms of education.

According to Professor, Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences Evgenya Semyonovna Polat: "Distance learning is a new form of education that already exists in many countries along with other forms of education - full-time, part-time, external study in the system of continuous education." Evgenya Semyonovna gives her definition of distance learning and defines it as "an independent form of learning, in which the interaction of the teacher and students, and students among themselves is carried out at a distance, and also covers components implemented using interactive Internet technologies"

Unlike traditional education, all educational activities in a distance format are provided to the student with the help of a variety of resources of the educational institution. These resources are able to manage the independent work of students with the help of teaching tools and computer programs. But, as

before, the leading role remains with the teacher. The distance form, along with distance learning, gradually increased the range of technologies used. The main principle of distance learning is direct interactive interaction between the teacher and students. This form is aimed at organizing, planning and conducting classes that are convenient and understandable for students in a virtual form.

Distance learning, according to many scientists, is able to keep the motivation to learn a foreign language, as it has the ability to individualize and diversify the learning process and includes modern technological tools that are interesting to students.

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